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Research Article

**STABILITY INDICATING METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION OF SAROGLITAZAR IN BULK AND
PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM BY REVERSE PHASE
HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY****Kasukurthi Rama Devi^{1*}, P.Prachet², Rama Rao Nadendla³**¹Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Chalapathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Chalapathi, Nagar, Lam, Guntur- 522034, Andhra Pradesh, India.**Article Received:** September 2019 **Accepted:** October 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

A simple, Precised, Accurate method was developed for the estimation of Saroglitazar by RP-HPLC technique. Chromatographic conditions used were stationary phase BDS100mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m, Mobile phase water: Acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:55 and flow rate was maintained at 1ml/min. The detection wave length was 214nm and column temperature was set to 30°C and the diluent was used as mobile phase Conditions were finalized for optimized method. The System suitability parameters were studied by injecting the standard five times and results were well under the acceptance criteria. Linearity study was carried out between 10 to 60 μ g/ml levels, R² value was found to be as 0.999. The Precision was found to be 1.13 for repeatability and 0.18 for intermediate precision. LOD and LOQ are 0.11 μ g/ml and 0.33 μ g/ml respectively. By using above method assay of marketed formulation was carried out 99.96% was present. Degradation studies of Saroglitazar were done, in all conditions purity threshold was more than purity angle and within the acceptable range.

Key words: HPLC, Saroglitazar, Method development, ICH Guidelines.**Corresponding author:****Kasukurthi Rama Devi,**

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INTRODUCTION:**High performance liquid chromatography [1,2]:**

In the Modern Pharmaceutical Industry, HPLC is the major and integral analytical tool applied in all stages of drug discovery, development, and production. HPLC is a special branch of Column Chromatography in which the Mobile phases is forced through the column at high speed.

Types of HPLC**Based on modes of chromatography**

- Normal phase chromatography
- Reversed phase chromatography

Based on principle of separation

- Adsorption chromatography
- Ion exchange chromatography
- Size exclusion chromatography
- Affinity chromatography
- Chiral phase chromatography

Based on elution technique

- Isocratic separation
- Gradient separation

Based on the scale of operation

- Analytical HPLC
- Preparative HPLC

Normal phase chromatography [3,4]:

- In normal phase mode the nature of stationary phase is polar and the mobile phase is non-polar.
- In this technique, non-polar compounds travel faster and are eluted first because of the lower affinity between the non-polar compounds and the stationary phase.
- Polar compounds are retained for longer times and take more time to elute because of their higher affinity with the stationary phase.
- Normal phase mode of separation is not generally used for pharmaceutical applications because most of the drug molecules are polar in nature and hence take longer time to elute.

Reversed phase chromatography [5,6]:

- It is the most popular mode for analytical and

Molecular Weight	:439.57
Molecular Formula	:C ₂₅ H ₂₉ NO ₄ S
Physical State	:Solid
Pka	:11.8
Category	:Anti diabetic
Solubility	:methanol

preparative separations of compounds of interest in chemical, biological, pharmaceutical, food and biomedical sciences.

- In this mode, the stationary phase is non-polar hydrophobic packing with octyl or octadecyl functional group bonded to silica gel and the mobile phase is a polar solvent.
- Polar compound gets eluted first and non-polar compounds are retained for longer time. As most of the drugs and pharmaceuticals are polar in nature, they are not retained for longer times and hence elute faster.
- The different columns used are octa decyl silane (ODS or C₁₈), octyl silane (C₈), butyl silane (C₄) etc. (in the order of increasing polarity of the stationary phase).

EQUIPMENTS AND REAGENTS:

HPLC instrument used was of WATERS HPLC 2965 SYSTEM with Auto Injector and pDA Detector. Software used is Empower, Micro balance (Sartorius), Vacuum filter, Methanol HPLC Grade (RANKEM), Acetonitrile HPLC Grade (RANKEM), HPLC grade Water (RANKEM), Ammonium Acetate.

DRUG PROFILE [7-9]:

Saroglitazar is a drug for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus and dyslipidemia. It is approved for use in India by the Drug Controller General of India. Saroglitazar is indicated for the treatment of diabetic dyslipidemia and hypertriglyceridemia with type 2 diabetes mellitus not controlled by statin therapy. In clinical studies, saroglitazar has demonstrated reduction of triglycerides (TG), LDL cholesterol, VLDL cholesterol, non-HDL cholesterol and an increase in HDL cholesterol a characteristic hallmark of Atherogenic Diabetic Dyslipidemia (ADD). It has also shown favourable glycemic control by reducing the fasting plasma glucose and HbA1c in diabetes patients.

Mechanism of action:

Saroglitazar is novel first in class drug which acts as a dual PPAR agonist at the subtypes α (alpha) and γ (gamma) of the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR). Agonist action at PPAR α lowers high blood triglycerides, and agonist action on PPAR γ improves insulin resistance and consequently lowers blood sugar.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT:**Optimized Chromatographic Conditions:**

Column	:ODS 150mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ .
Mobile phase	:Amoniumacetate : Acetonitrile (50:50A)
Flow rate	:1.0 ml/min
Detector	:PDA 290nm
Temperature	:30 $^{\circ}$ C
Injection Volume	:10 μ L

	Peak Name	RT	Area	% Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Saroglitazar	2.515	1472224	100.00	2344	1.16

Fig-1-Optimized chromatogram

Observation: Saroglitazareluted with good peak shape and retention time and tailing was passed.

VALIDATION PARAMETERS:

Table-1- System Suitability Parameters

S no	Peak Name	RT	Area	USP Plate	USP Tailing
1	Saroglitazar	2.489	1500030	2351	1.18
2	Saroglitazar	2.496	1513010	2323	1.16
3	Saroglitazar	2.497	1487495	2340	1.17
4	Saroglitazar	2.503	1474122	2373	1.17
5	Saroglitazar	2.504	1477221	2359	1.14
6	Saroglitazar	2.505	1477873	2373	1.17
Mean			1488292		
Std. Dev.			15371.1		
% RSD			1.0		

Intermediate precision Chromatograms

	Peak Name	RT	Area	% Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Saroglitazar	2.490	1588712	100.00	2311	1.13

Fig-2- Interday Precision Chromatogram

Table-3-Intermediate precision Chromatogram**Peak Name: Saroglitazar**

	Peak Name	RT	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Saroglitazar	2.489	1490141	2356	1.16
2	Saroglitazar	2.496	1481565	2344	1.15
3	Saroglitazar	2.497	1478263	2347	1.16
4	Saroglitazar	2.503	1466620	2378	1.17
5	Saroglitazar	2.504	1463046	2366	1.16
6	Saroglitazar	2.505	1483208	2369	1.16
Mean			1477140		
Std. Dev.			10353.9		
% RSD			0.7		

Table 4 -Linearity Concentration and Response

Linearity Level (%)	Concentration (ppm)	Peak Area
0	0	0
25	10	366884
50	20	772421
75	30	1153115
100	40	1481282
125	50	1902234
150	60	2257773

Table-5-Accuracy Data

% Level	Amount Spiked ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Total amount found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
50%	20	60.17	20.17	100.84	99.94%
	20	59.88	19.88	99.39	
	20	59.96	19.96	99.81	
100%	40	80.58	40.58	101.46	
	40	80.35	40.35	100.88	
	40	79.36	39.36	98.40	
150%	60	98.98	58.98	98.31	
	60	100.08	60.08	100.13	

Table-6-Repeatability and Intermediate Precision Data

S.No	Day 1/ Repeatability	Day 2/ Intermediate precision
1	1500356	1490141
2	1482420	1481565
3	1479016	1478263
4	1502240	1466620
5	1509293	1463046
6	1478203	1483208
AVG	1491921	1477141
STDEV	13597.1	10353.7
%RSD	0.9	0.7

Table-7- Recovery Studies data

Parameter	%RSD
Flow rate(-0.9)	0.86
Flow rate(+1.1)	0.34
Mobile phase(-5%)	0.13
Mobile phase (+5%)	0.03
Temperature (-25)	0.3
Temperature (+35)	0.6

Table-8- Degradation Data of Saroglitazar

S.NO	Degradation Condition	AREA	%ASSAY	AMMOUNT DEGRADED %
1	Acid	1351419	90.7	9.3
2	Alkali	1395101	93.6	6.4
3	Oxidation	1421693	95.4	4.6
4	Thermal	1453736	97.6	2.4
5	UV	1472197	98.8	1.2
6	Water	1351419	99.5	0.5

Table-9- Assay Studies

	Sample No	% Assay
1		100.71
2		99.51
3.		99.28
4.		100.84
5.		101.31
6.		99.22
AVG		100.14
STDEV		0.91
%RSD		0.91

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Chromatographic conditions used are stationary phase ODS 150mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m. Mobile phase buffer: acetonitrile in the ratio of 50:50 and flow rate was maintained at 1ml/min, detection wave length was 290nm, column temperature was set to 30°C and diluent was mobile phase. Conditions were finalized as optimized method. System suitability parameters were studied by injecting the standard five times and results were well under the acceptance criteria. Linearity study was carried out between 25% to 150 % levels, R² value was found to be as 0.999. Precision was found to be 0.9 for repeatability and 0.7 for intermediate precision. LOD and LOQ are 0.06 μ g/ml and 0.19 μ g/ml respectively. By using above method assay of marketed formulation was carried out 99.94% was present

REFERENCES:

1. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saroglitazar>
2. <http://www.scbt.com/datasheet-205690-Saroglitazar.html>
3. <http://www.rxlist.com/zetia-drug/clinical-pharmacology.htm>
4. <http://www.scbt.com/datasheet-217671-Saroglitazar.html>
5. Poonam G. Determination of monodirectional permeability of ZYH1 across Caco2 cell monolayer using LC-MS/MS. Ahmedabad: Cadila Healthcare Ltd; 2011.
6. Robert RH, Michael AL, Sunder M, et al. Effects of the dual peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- α/γ agonist aleglitazar on risk of cardiovascular disease in patients with type 2 diabetes (SYNCHRONY). *Lancet*, 2009; 374: 126–35.
7. Fievet, C.; Fruchart, J.; Staels, B. "PPAR α and PPAR γ dual agonists for the treatment of type 2 diabetes and the metabolic syndrome". *Current Opinion in Pharmacology*, 2006; 6 (6): 606–614.
8. R. G Chatwal, Anand K.S. High performance liquid chromatography. Instrumental methods of chemical analysis, 5th ed; Himalaya publishers: Mumbai, 2010; 2.570-2.629.
9. B. K Sharma, High performance liquid chromatography. Instrumental methods of chemical analysis, 24th ed; Goel publishers: Meerut, 2005; 295-300.